

Plant regeneration frequency from wild rice inflorescence cultured by two different methods. Wuhan, China.

Species	Genome	Origin	No.	Method 1		Method 2			
				Calli transferred (no.)	Regenerated plants (no.)	Regeneration frequency (%)	Panicles cultured (no.)	Regenerated plants (no.)	Regeneration frequency (%)
<i>Oryza rufipogon</i>	AA	China	2	-	-	-	20	18	90.0
			3	8	0	0	-	-	-
			4	18	0	0	22	21	95.5
			5	18	2	11.1	35	26	74.3
			6	13	0	0	15	8	50.0
				17	10	58.8	17	13	76.5
<i>O. longstaminata</i>	A ¹ A ¹	Stolon Philippines	15	0	0	-	-	-	
			20	4	20.0	-	-	-	
<i>O. punctata</i>	BBCC	India	12	0	0	-	-	-	
<i>O. officinalis</i>	CC	China	14	0	0	-	-	-	
			16	0	0	37	0	0	
			34	10	29.4	-	-	-	
<i>O. eichingeri</i>	CC	Sri Lanka	15	0	0	30	12	40.0	
<i>O. alta</i>	CCDD	Brazil	18	10	55.6	27	18	66.7	
<i>O. latifolia</i>	CCDD	Mexico	21	3	14.3	23	12	52.2	
<i>O. brachyantha</i>	FF	Zambia	15	0	0	-	-	-	
<i>O. meyeriana</i>	?	China	24	14	58.3	15	12	80.0	

^a - not tested.

was only 11.1% in the normal type of *O. rufipogon* (number 5), but 58.8% in the stolon type of the same species.

In the second culture method, plantlets regenerated directly from the young panicles of wild rice that were cultured on the differentiating medium. Six species including 10

accessions were tested. Plantlets were obtained from five species except *O. officinalis*. The regeneration frequency was generally higher in this method than in the method via callus differentiation. Compared with plantlet differentiation via callus, direct regeneration of young panicles was much simpler

and the time needed shorter. Direct regeneration might present less risk to somatic variation than is common in in vitro tissue culture of the plant. Therefore, this method has potential in micropropagation, genetic manipulation, and cryopreservation of *Oryza* germplasm. ■

Determination of suitable time to select trisomics induced from anther culture of autotetraploid rice

Wu Minsheng, Genetic and Breeding Department, China Agricultural University, Beijing 100094, China

Use of primary trisomics has played an important role in genetics and breeding of rice. A great number of trisomics could be induced through anther culture of autotetraploid rice. In earlier work, trisomics of rice selected according to auricle distances from -2.5 cm to + 2.5 cm resulted in low selection efficiency. This paper reports on an efficient time to select trisomics.

Relationship between auricle distance and frequency of anthers in various phases.

	Metaphase		Metaphase	Abnormal
	Trisomic	Diploid	(%)	(%)
Auricle distance (cm) ^a	-1.5 to + 1.5		-	-
Observed number (bottle)	20	59	68.1	31.9

^aDistance between auricle of the flag leaf and that of the next leaf from the flag leaf.

From 116 bottle anthers of young panicles of autotetraploid rice, we selected 100 panicles randomly per bottle. The results were as follows: 1) when auricle distance was from -1.5 cm to + 1.5 cm, all anthers were in metaphase and trisomics or diploids could be determined; 2) when auricle distance was from -2.5 cm to + 2.5 cm,

only 68.1% of the anthers were in metaphase; and 3) when auricle distance was from -2.5 cm to -1.5 cm or from + 1.5 cm to + 2.5 cm, no anthers were in metaphase (see table).

We concluded that an auricle distance from -1.5 cm to + 1.5 cm was better than from -2.5 cm to + 2.5 cm for selecting trisomics. ■